

**THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FUTURE
TECHNOLOGY**

¹Gaybulloyev E.E.,

²Kudratillaev M.B.,

³Siddikov B.N.

¹Department of Applied Informatics, KIMYO International University in
Tashkent, Tashkent

^{2,3}Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-
Khwarizmi, Tashkent

Abstract. This research paper illuminates the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in future technology. Artificial intelligence is a field of computer science that aims to create mental capabilities similar to human intelligence in machines and systems. In recent decades, AI has undergone significant breakthroughs and has become a key factor in the development of modern technologies.

Key words. AI, Internet of Things, Cyber security, COVID-19, healthcare technology, numerous technologies.

I. Introduction

This paper examines how AI will play a crucial role in various domains of future technology. In the field of medicine, artificial intelligence will help improve disease diagnosis and prediction, optimize patient treatment, and support medical decisions based on big data and image analysis. In the realm of autonomous transportation, AI will play a vital role in creating safe and efficient transportation management systems, leading to a reduction in accidents and improved mobility.

Artificial intelligence will also find application in the manufacturing sector, where automation and process optimization will be made possible through self-learning AI systems. In the energy sector, artificial intelligence will enable more efficient energy distribution, enhancing energy efficiency and supporting environmental sustainability.

Furthermore, the role of AI in the development of future technology will extend to areas such as finance, robotics, education, and entertainment. AI will enhance the analytical capabilities of financial institutions, create new types of interactive and intelligent robots, revolutionize traditional models of education, and offer new forms of virtual reality and entertainment experiences.

I. Artificial intelligence today. Future technology for us

Artificial intelligence (AI) is without a doubt one of today's most disruptive technologies, having a tremendous influence on our daily lives [1]. According to a Valuates Reports assessment, the AI industry is quickly developing, with a projected value of slightly less than \$170 billion in 2025. To far, AI has produced solutions in a range of fields, including finance, marketing, media, advertising, information technology, and robotics. Furthermore, AI has already proven its value in a number of academic disciplines such as natural language processing, computer vision, and recommendation engines. As a result, in most cases, these fields and AI cannot be treated separately.

Prior to the 2000s, even computers were incapable of executing most AI algorithms, but that has changed dramatically in the recent decade. We now utilize AI-powered applications and technologies in our daily lives more than ever before. 5G, cloud computing, big data, developments in sensors, open source ecosystem, and novel learning-based methodologies (e.g., deep neural networks, attention models) have accelerated the emergence of AI during the last decade [2]. This article will concentrate on the AI-assisted future technologies that are projected to develop and become more widespread in the near future. As a result, the implications of AI on cyber security, health technology, and autonomous cars will be investigated, as these technologies are among the most promising AI-assisted technologies.

People are sharing more information with organizations than ever before, as more industries harness the power of digitization [3]. Companies are feeling more responsible for data security as the volume of data stored and processed grows

dramatically. Because of cloud technologies and cheaper processing power, large-scale cyber-attacks, frequently involving thousands of bots, have become possible. A small-scale cyber attack can cost millions of dollars and ruin a company's reputation. As a prominent field, cyber security can address such issues.

Cyber security is expected to be popular in the next decades. According to International Data Corporation (IDC), (cyber) security investment would reach \$174.7 billion in 2024, growing at an 8.1 percent compound annual growth rate (CAGR) between 2020 and 2024. Users, on the other hand, appear to be the weakest link in the security chain, since hackers may easily trick them with a number of approaches [4]. Nonetheless, due to a new study subject of AI in cyber security, cyber-defense has been strengthened using AI applications. According to Pranav Patil's study, having the capacity to use more AI than criminals is critical in cyber security. As a result, establishing intelligent cyber security solutions for cyber defense is vital.

III. Application of Artificial Intelligence in Various Fields

As a result of IoT (Internet of Things), mobile health applications, and digital transformation in the healthcare industry, medical data is rising and getting more complex. As a result, future health tech will surely incorporate AI-based healthcare solutions (or healthcare technology). The healthcare business is becoming increasingly data-driven and AI-driven [5]. AI-enabled solutions, according to one study, save expenses, improve efficiency, and improve health outcomes.

According to experts, AI, along with robotics, is changing the healthcare environment, and that AI is the most disruptive technology in the sector. In addition to employing it in traditional medicine, AI can help limit the spread of future pandemics like COVID-19 by demystifying the virus's protein structures, anticipating the efficacy of immunizations, or accelerating clinical trials of beneficial drug discoveries.

Furthermore, the number of AI-related enterprises in healthcare technology is increasing, which is reshaping the industry in a number of countries. India is a well-known example, where the number of AI-based healthcare enterprises has increased

dramatically in recent years. In another study, Garbuio stated that there are three stages of AI-mediated healthcare: assisted intelligence, improved intelligence, and autonomous intelligence [6]. According to Garbuio, autonomous intelligence is a future stage in which AI will make human-independent decisions and hospitals would be devoid of physicians. Finally, in the future, AI technology will most likely be merged with healthcare technologies, touching the lives of millions, if not billions, of people.

The term autonomy derives from old Greek, when it was used as political rhetoric to denote self-governance or authoritative independence. Today, this term refers to a computer or intelligent agent that acts independently of human supervision. Autonomy does not need to address any present problems; rather, it redefines, extends, and, in some cases, establishes entirely new mission areas. According to Ted Krueger, brute force programming cannot manage the high amount of environmental complexity, thus agents should evaluate context, learn new inputs, and act autonomously.

Autonomous vehicles based on artificial intelligence (AI) have gone a long way in the recent decade, including autonomous robots, drones, and buses. Azad et al., for example, described entirely autonomous buses and observed that a growing amount of research on bus transportation and full autonomy is being conducted [7]. AI-assisted autonomous vehicles will certainly become more common in our daily lives in the future, since they remove human mistake and boost efficiency.

Over the last decade, advancements in numerous technologies such as cloud computing, big data, and mobile computing have all contributed to the advancement of AI. AI then played an important part in numerous academic domains as well as in a wide range of enterprises. While certain businesses (e.g., finance, media, marketing, advertising, and IT) have effectively implemented AI principles, others are only getting started. This article discussed three technologies (and their respective industries) that have the potential to integrate a variety of AI-based approaches in the near future. While all of the technologies listed (cyber security, health technology, and self-driving vehicles) have been popular for some time and now use a range of AI-based approaches, it is expected that AI will have a stronger influence on these technologies

in the coming years. As a result, artificial intelligence will play a vital role in the progress of these technologies, culminating in worldwide transformation.

IV. Conclusion

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays and will continue to play a crucial role in the development of future technology. Over the past decades, AI has undergone significant breakthroughs, enabling its penetration into various spheres of our lives.

AI is already demonstrating its value in the field of medicine by improving disease diagnosis, predicting outcomes, and optimizing patient treatment. In the realm of autonomous transportation, AI ensures the safety and efficiency of transportation management systems by eliminating human errors and reducing accidents.

In the manufacturing sector, AI enables automation and optimization of processes, resulting in increased productivity and efficiency. This leads to improved product quality and reduced costs. The energy sector also benefits from the application of AI, allowing for efficient energy distribution and increased energy efficiency. This contributes to resource conservation and the mitigation of negative environmental impact.

However, the role of AI is not limited to these industries alone. It exerts significant influence in finance, robotics, education, and entertainment as well. The analytical capabilities of AI assist financial institutions in making more accurate decisions, while intelligent robots become increasingly interactive and tailored to our needs.

The future of technology undoubtedly depends on the development and application of artificial intelligence. AI will continue to bring forth new possibilities, enhance efficiency, and create innovations across many domains. This necessitates continued research, the establishment of ethical and safe practices, and collaboration among scientific, industrial, and societal sectors.

V. Used literature

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